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Credible Leadership and Leader-Follower Relationship in Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomosho

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Abstract

Many organisations operate through periods of change and uncertainties which require quality leadership to help achieve organisational goals and gain competitive edge while ensuring long term sustainability. Credible leadership has been described as a style of leadership that can effectively give credence and competitive edge to an organisation. Credibility has also been reported to have positive effect on many organisational constructs such as job satisfaction, commitment, and citizenship behaviour. This present study seeks to explore the role of credible leadership on the leader-follower relationship in one of Nigeria's tertiary educational institutions. The qualitative study is conducted using three highly ranked educational leaders from the Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomosho. Responses from the participants were analysed for cogent patterns using thematic analysis. The findings show that leaders' conflict resolution ability, followers' development or competence building and open communication predicated on the willingness to receive feedbacks determine the relationship between educational leaders and their followers. A recommendation is made for future research to conduct quantitative empirical research on this study's findings.

Keywords: Credible Leadership, Organisational Relationship, Education

Introduction

Many organisations operate in markets or industries characterised by change and uncertainties and leadership is required not just for achieving organisational goals and gaining competitive edge but also for sustaining the organisation in the long run. For these organisations, achieving sustainability is prioritised over short-term profitability (Prakash, Prasad and Nair, 2021). Studies have shown that more than organisational strategies, planning or structure, the credibility of the leader determines the sustainability of the organisation (Van Droffelaar and Jacobs, 2017; Prakash *et al.*, 2021). This is because credible leadership which is synonymous to authentic leadership has been linked to cordial leader-employees' relationship, increase in employees' positive organisational citizenship behaviour, commitment and satisfaction in organisations (Liu *et al.*, 2015; Iqbal *et al.*, 2019; Amran, 2023). Among many attributes and characteristics, Kouzes and Posner (2011) described an authentic or credible leader as honest, vulnerable, transparent, genuine and self-aware in attitude, character and conduct. These attributes influence how employees in the organisation and stakeholders within and outside see and approach the leader. However, Avolio and Walumbwa (2014) claimed that authentic leadership will not only make the leader appear credible but will equally influence the characters and competencies of the followers. This claim is corroborated by Van Droffelar and Jacobs' (2017) study which shows that authentic leadership increases resilience, tenacity, confidence and hope in followers, which in turn brings a positive ethical climate that ensure cordial relationships in the organisation.

Higher educational institutions have evolved over the years into complex organisations with complex needs and goals as they endeavor to adapt to and meet the need of a changing environment. Hence, the demand for effective leadership in educational institutions has also increased. This means that school leaders now have to take on several roles in leading their organisation to effectiveness and sustainability. Considering the fact that educational institutions play a crucial role in the development of other organisations as the crucible where various organisational leaders are made, the need for credibility becomes more pronounced (Gentry *et al.*, 2013). Generally, educational leadership involves community building through the development of teachers and students so that they can contribute better to the community (Cordeiro and Cunningham, 2014). In other words, if schools want to develop students to become credible leaders in the society and organisations, they must as well provide credible/authentic

leadership in the institutions. Building a friendly climate in schools where followers can freely relate with leaders help to ensure social justice and equity. This study therefore seeks to examine the relationship between credible/authentic leadership and leader-follower relationship in an educational institution.

Objectives of the Study

This qualitative study aims to investigate the relationship between credible leadership and leader-follower relationship in Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomosho. The specific objectives are to:

- i. explore educational leaders understanding of authentic/credible leadership;
- ii. identify common experience that improves educational leaders' credibility; and
- iii. determine the influence of credibility on leader-followers' relationship in educational institutions.

Review of Relevant Literature: Conceptualisation of Credible Leadership

Authentic or credible leadership can be said to derive its origin from ancient Greece where a maxim about individuals' understanding themselves became popular. Authenticity in leadership is evident when leaders understand themselves and ensure congruence in values, attitudes, convictions and conduct (Arda *et al.*, 2016; Lisbona *et al.*, 2021). Van Draffelaar and Jacobs (2017) described authentic leadership as a leadership construct that shares similarities with spiritual, transformational, ethical and servant leadership theories. These similarities can be adduced to the emphasis of these theories on the essence or morals on the personality of a leader. To illustrate these similarities further, Gentry *et al.* (2013) noted that authentic or credible leadership is all about the congruence between a leader's actions and convictions both in private and in public. Hinojosa *et al.* (2014) described credible leadership as a theory of leadership which emphasises the need for leaders to have awareness of how their thoughts and conducts are perceived by others. This form of leadership also involves leaders being conscious of their respective contexts, strengths, weaknesses, values and moral convictions (Kouzes and Posner, 2011; Fox, 2015). Such leaders are hopeful, confident, resilient, optimistic and exemplify motivation to followers. Followers are quick to identify that there is synergy between the verbal expressions and lifestyle of such leaders (Hinojosa *et al.*, 2014; Baquero *et al.*, 2015). The credibility of a leader is evident when such leader is able to offer psychological support to the followers (Sarkar, 2019). Authentic leaders are leaders who believe in their followers and are enthusiastic in their development. The positivity of authentic leaders according to Gentry *et al.* (2013) is the reason for high performance and effectiveness of organisations. This implies that the credibility of the leader not only influences the character of the leader but also influences followers and increase the capacity of organisations led by such leaders. Kouzes and Pozner (2011) identified a leader's ability to offer positive motivation to the followers as a distinct characteristic of authentic leader.

Dimensions of Credible Leadership

Credible leadership can be explained as a multidimensional leadership construct which consists of four areas. These components of authentic leadership, according to Hinojosa *et al.* (2014), include self-awareness, relational transparency, balanced processing and the internal moral perspective. According to Kouzes and Posner (2011), self-awareness is a component of authentic/credible leadership which explains the intentionality of leaders. Self-awareness refers to the ability of authentic leaders to demonstrate understanding about personal strengths and weaknesses. Self-awareness is not limited to discovery of strengths and flaws, Steffens *et al.* (2021) noted that through self-awareness, authentic leaders understand their talents, vision, mission, core values, convictions, beliefs and aspirations. According to Semendo (2017), self-awareness makes a leader conscious of his feelings and how such feelings are perceived by colleagues and followers. While describing self-awareness as a component of authentic leadership, Gardner *et al.* (2006) emphasised that authentic leaders are sensitive due to their awareness of how their actions and conduct impacts the actions of others. Similarly, Gardner *et al.* (2006) defined self-awareness as the interplay of a leader's convictions, core values, attitudes, motivations, emotions and sense of identity. The sense of self-awareness of authentic leaders allows them to prioritise honesty, vulnerability and transparency. Self-aware leaders are willing to accommodate and accept the viewpoints of followers as well as show humility by properly handling feedback (Steffens *et al.*, 2021).

Relational transparency can be described as the ability of authentic leaders to be vulnerable, open and transparent in their interactions with others. Relational transparency entails leaders presenting themselves with a sense of security (Iszatt-White *et al.*, 2021). This sense of security makes authentic leaders to be genuine, open and transparent. Relational transparency makes leaders open in such a way that leaders are willing to share information with followers without any bias or sentiment. The ability of authentic leaders to be relationally transparent positively impacts leader-follower relationship by increasing the trust followers have in their leaders (Kouzes and Posner, 2011). Relational transparency involves leaders presenting their true selves without pretense or hypocrisy. Similarly, relational transparency is the ability of leaders to avoid dual nature and dichotomy of values (Steffens *et al.*, 2021). Relational transparency makes leaders to act without inhibition thereby making them willing to admit mistakes, accept criticism and constructive feedback. Authentic leaders prioritise listening to followers and being willing to consider the opinions and suggestions of others (Van Draffelaar and Jacobs, 2017). The third component of authentic leadership, balanced processing, is the ability of leaders to be objective. Leaders reflect balanced processing by giving careful consideration to different choices and opinions during decision-making (Steffens *et al.*, 2021). Balanced processing implies that authentic leaders are competent in objective analysis and critical thinking. When leaders employ balanced processing, the best opinion not their personal opinion is implemented (Williams *et al.*, 2021). According to Gardner *et al.* (2006), balanced processing is self-regulatory because it allows authentic leaders to harmonize core values with motives and actions. To be balanced in processing demands, leaders are willing to evaluate information and opinion of followers without bias and in an ethical manner (Steffens *et al.*, 2021). The fourth component of authentic leadership is internalised moral perspective. Internalized moral is synonymous to self-discipline or self-regulation. Internalised moral perspective is the ability of authentic leaders to set personal standards (Kouzes and Posner, 2011). Authentic leaders set internal standards and seek to resolve inconsistencies in values and conduct. Leaders with a balanced moral perspective allow their core values and moral standards to influence their attitudes, actions and conduct (Williams *et al.*, 2021). For leaders to have a balanced moral perspective, they need to accept responsibility for their morals, actions and decisions. Hence, such leaders are guided by set personal standards and not pressure or sentiments from any individual, group or organisation. As a result of internalised moral perspective, leaders are able to make decisions and act in ways that are consistent with their core values (Lisbona *et al.*, 2021).

The Influence of Credible Leadership on Leader-Follower Relationship

Alok (2014) and Steffens *et al.* (2021) observed that authentic leadership has been discovered to have positive impact on individuals, teams, followers, leaders and different forms of organisations. Mrak *et al.* (2021) observed that organisational performance and effectiveness improved significantly as a result of authentic leadership. Lisbona *et al.* (2021) noted that authentic leadership increased initiative of employees, team culture and reduced burnout of employee. Wirawan *et al.* (2020) attributed improved job fulfillment and satisfaction as well as increased employee engagement to application of authentic leadership practices in organisations. Semendo (2017) explained that high levels of followers' creativity are evident when leaders are authentic and strong, lasting relationships are built between leaders and followers. The following attributes of credible/authentic leaders emphasises the quality of relationship between leaders and followers in organisations:

Open Communication and Willingness to Receive and Give Feedbacks

Lisak *et al.* (2016) noted that organisations that experience peak performance from their teams always have an effective communication system. Effective communication between leaders and followers is essential because a leader must help followers to see and go beyond their self-interest by emphasizing collective interests which promotes the eagerness of teams to engage one another as they share the same goals and objectives as set by the leader. It is imperatively important that leaders within organisations guide team members to see one another as insiders and help to build trust between the different teams and team members to promote the exchange of their different cultural perspectives, skills, knowledge and

values in achieving innovative outcomes (Stahl *et al.*, 2010). Lisak *et al.* (2016) opined that a shared innovation goal motivates team members and help the different teams to recognise themselves as different sets of a bigger team that must be united to achieve this goal. The study also suggested that a shared innovation goal amplifies the use of a shared and common language which serves as an important alignment process for different individuals to achieve peak performance in a cohesive environment. Hajro *et al.* (2017) noted that the diversity in perspectives, beliefs, values and skill sets of individuals in an organisation necessitates communication with one another, sharing the same goal through assertive, cooperative or oscillatory knowledge exchange. Authentic or credible leaders have been asserted to have good communication skills which make followers believe in not just the leaders' vision but their own selves and abilities. One of the communication skills that credible leaders possess is the ability to process feedback, and also be able to appraise events, experiences and changes in order to find general principles that guide such events which is a way of simplifying the problem and finding a common solution that will fit all situations (Mrak *et al.*, 2021).

Effective Conflict Resolution

The direct impact of communication between teams and leaders in an organisation can be measured by the level of conflict resolution and cohesiveness within and between the groups in the organisation. Conflict arises in organisations as a result of differences in the priorities and diverse opinions or demands of individuals within the organisation (Stahl *et al.*, 2010). Credible leaders because of their high self-esteem and competence will likely use humour which may help to diffuse complex situations while they stay calm and professional (Nelson and Campbell, 2018). Such leaders know how to deal with people who seem difficult because there is high tendency of having such people in an organisation. However, beyond dealing with difficult employees, authentic leaders have good listening skills and try as much as possible to relate with employees beyond work issues to understand their perspectives, thoughts, emotions and attitudes (Van Draffelaar and Jacobs, 2017).

Credible leaders leading a multicultural team must always find a common ground with each of the followers in the organisation regardless of whatever cultural backgrounds, exposures, values or beliefs they may have. Conflicts may arise in a multicultural organisation as a result of lack of respect and mutual trust between culturally different employees who may think that one culture supersedes the other (Antonakis and Day, 2018). Therefore, managers and leaders within such an organisation must take deliberate and intentional steps to build trust and mutual respect between the diverse culturally different teams. Leaders must not only stop at this point but also help and guide team members in managing and handling conflict within the organisation. This creates a healthy environment where the employees or team members can always take initiative in resolving conflict on their own for the progress and benefits of the organisation (Daft, 2015). In order to avoid organisational decline through persisting conflict, leaders must formulate strategies that emphasise equality and inclusion of people from all backgrounds. Such strategies may include rotation of power and positions, decentralisation of authority, training and seminars on conflict resolution (Hofstede *et al.*, 2010).

Followers' Development and Competence Building

Authentic leaders possess exceptional skills and high competence which is evident from organisational performance. The performance of authentic leaders makes followers willing to submit and learn from them (Kouzes and Posner, 2011). However, the authentic leader is not only willing to train or teach the followers his or her personal skills but also provide avenues for followers to learn from one another (Campos & Rueda, 2019). Team members in an organisation possess values, perspectives, cognition and behavior pattern which can lead to innovation within the organisation and leader-team member's interaction is essential to help people learn from one another, grow and align their values and expectations with that of the organisation (Antonakis and Day, 2018). The credible leader is basically altruistic and seeks consistently the holistic development of followers in the organisation. A team-inclusive approach in an organisation helps to bring together the skills, experiences, knowledge and perspectives of members to grow the organisation into having a competitive advantage in a global market (Zweifei, 2013).

Multicultural organisations share ideas, thought, perspectives and knowledge between multicultural and diverse teams to foster the growth of the organisations.

Methodology

The research design for this study is the interpretive case study. The interpretive case study is influenced by the social constructivist theoretical framework. This framework is based on the assumption that reality is socially constructed (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). In research, social constructivists suggest that reality is multiple. Based on the nature of this study, the qualitative approach was most appropriate as it allowed the researcher ease of access to the research setting and participants to understand an event within the context (Palinkas *et al.*, 2015). The participants in this study were education leaders specifically 3 principal lecturers, theological educators and instructional leaders in the Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso, Nigeria. These education leaders were selected through purposive sampling with the aim of identifying information rich sites. Thus, the leaders were identified based on their experience, reputation and integrity which are characteristic of authentic leadership. These leaders were also chosen based on their leadership experience and position in the institution and thus interaction with the phenomenon of interest. They were also selected based on their ability to give expert opinion on their leadership experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Ethical approval and consent were obtained from the institution and the participants prior to the study. Data was collected using semi-structured interviews to explore participants’ perspectives drawn from their experiences (Jamshed, 2014). An interview protocol was prepared and reviewed by experienced researchers and lecturers and amended. Appointments for an interview were then booked and participants engaged in 40-minute interviews within the institution. The interviews were read, transcribed and endorsed by participants. They were then subjected to data analysis through thematic analysis (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Thematic analysis in qualitative research is a process of identifying patterns and then themes within data and this is interpreted to give meaning to the research question (Palinkas *et al.*, 2015). Thematic analysis is a way of finding correlation and patterns between concepts or data that are not necessarily related. The researcher uses intuition and reflection to organise data into themes or codes with the goal of making meanings or developing a story from the analysed texts (Jamshe, 2014). Codes or themes in the text can interrelate to form categories or order. This form of analysis is often used for coding emotions and experiences (Palinkas *et al.*, 2015).

Research Findings

Recordings of interviews from participants are listened to and summarized into tables and the summary of participants’ response for each question is analysed for themes relating to autocratic or credible leadership. Identified themes are then discussed in relation to extant literature.

Educational Leaders’ Understanding of Credible Leadership

Table 1 What is your understanding of credible leadership?

Interviewee	Response
1	Credible leadership is such in which the leader leads with honesty, integrity with believable evidence of accountability that brings about trust, confidence and motivate team spirit in the followers; whereby the vision and goal of the organisation is achieved through effective cooperation of all.
2	Credible leadership is the one who is charismatic and who has a good character – charisma and character (C.A.C) (anyone who has charisma but does not have character will go fast in ministry but will not go far. Credible leader is a man upon whom there is grace and who balances it with impeccable character and integrity. He is a man who means what he says and who says what he means. This follows the life of Jesus Christ who lives without pretense.

3.	Credible leadership is someone who is trustworthy, someone who does what is highly commendable.
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Table 2: In your opinion what are the quality of a credible leader?

Interviewee	Response
1	Honesty, Integrity, Accountability, Confidence, Courage, Personal Development, Team Spirit
2	Character, Competence and Commitment, impeccability, integrity, honesty, transparency
3.	Being likeable, humble, honest, teachable, ready to take advice, ready to caution, patience, someone who is tolerant, not aggressive

Table 3: Please explain the qualities of credible leadership which you feel are most important?

Interviewee	Response
1	Honesty: this is a quality of transparency in action and words. It creates a nexus between the personal life of a leader and his/her life. It leads to ethical behavior in work environment. Accountability: the leader acknowledges and accept responsibility for his/her action and decisions. It is important because the leader accept when they make mistake and it gives the follower the need to own the vision of the organisation without bias.
2	Character: This is who we are, what we do that there is no fake, no pretense Competence: This is putting the right peg in the right hole Commitment: It is paying the price to get the prize
3	Trustworthy, humility, honesty, respect advice – who carry others along and take advice from others, kind

Table 4: What are your core values as a credible leader?

Interviewee	Response
1	Character development informed by some biblical principles Strength of relationship with God and man Life investment: The greatest investment is the investment made on others. That which I do to make others live and fulfill their God-given destiny.
2	Integrity, hard work, transparency, accountability, discipline, synergy
3.	Academic excellence, spiritual vibrancy, competent ministry, God first in all things, giving the best in all that I do, sincerity to God, sincerity in term of my relationship to others, trustfulness and honesty

Emergent themes were leading with honesty, accountable to followers, trusted by followers, confident, motivating, visionary and good character.

Leading with Honesty

All the three participants agreed that credible leaders are known for their honesty as a participant put it thus “a man who means what he says and who says what he means.” Participants described honesty as a quality of transparency in action and words. This corroborates Gentry *et al.*'s (2013) statement that credibility entails acting with authenticity and honesty in speech and conduct. To have credibility as a leader is to be consistent in speaking the truth, being genuine and sincere in actions. Participants' statement also corroborates Gardner *et al.*'s (2005) assertion which noted that development of integrity involves avoidance of pretense and hypocrisy.

Motivating

Participants emphasised the ability to motivate followers as a characteristic of credible leaders. Similarly, participants itemized the fact that credible leaders are usually highly commended by followers which means that followers hold the leader in high esteem. This finding reiterates Kouzes and Posner’s (2011) submission that authentic leaders inspire and motivate others. This is further supported by Oginde’s (2011) description of credible leaders’ ability to inspire the actions of colleagues and followers.

Good Character

Also, participants mentioned that credible leaders always show and develop good character. Similarly, a participant mentioned trustworthiness as a cogent attribute of credible leaders. Singh et al. (2020) noted that credible leaders are morally consistent and have concern for the growth and development of the followers. Credible leaders lead by example in morality and ethical stand on issues based on convictions instead of popularity and sentiments (Kouzes and Posner, 2011).

Competence

One of the participants described competence as putting the right peg into the right hole. This corroborates Kouzes and Posner’s (2011) assertion that credible leaders have a perpetual personal drive for excellence.

Educational Leaders’ Experiences that Develop Leadership Credibility

Table 5: What are the activities that contribute to Credibility in Leaders?

Interviewee	Responses
1	Personal/Capacity Development, Dependability, Focus, Team Relationship
2	Christlikeness – the foundation of any credible leader is Christ Vision for the mission: a credible leader must have vision – mission without vision is illusion Discipline, Patience to carry others along, Accountability
3	sharing ideas, principle of mutual respect, understanding others uniqueness and accepting others as they are

Table 6 Share experiences or activities that help your development of credibility

Interviewee	Response
1	As a theological educator, capacity development through reading, tackling new tasks and taking and improving on feedback is very essential for me if my leadership will not become stale and irrelevant. Team relationship is a principle I hold tenaciously for student not to see me as boss-teacher rather than a co-learner. It also creates for me an environment of friendliness in my administrative function as a head of department
2.	While I was a pastor for 18years, I was always conscious of my integrity, secondly, I have vision for the mission God gave, I have learnt patience over time, the more I know God, the more I slow down. I am accountable, every session, my students evaluate me. They design questionnaire about me and fill it faithfully, so I know I am accountable

Emergent themes were capacity development, team relationship, Christ-likeness, strategic thinking and vision casting, discipline, patience, accountability, mutual respect.

Capacity Development

A participant stated capacity development as key component of his leadership which brings competence and then credibility. The participant describes activities such as reading, working on feedbacks and

looking for new demanding tasks as capacity development. This opinion corroborates Kouzes and Posner's (2011) statement that followers are attracted to the improving performance of a leader and are willing to trust and submit to the perceived successful experience of such a leader.

Team Relationship

One of the participants is willing to create a friendly learning environment by encouraging students and staffs to be free and open with one another. This has been observed by the participant to make followers trust him more. This observation can be explained by Stahl *et al's.* (2010) submission that authentic leaders within organisation guide team members to see one another as insiders and help to build trust between the different team members to promote the exchange of their different perspectives, skills, knowledge and values in achieving innovative outcomes. Similar to team relationship is mutual respect which participants report to have positive effect on their development of credible leadership.

Accountability

A participant shared how he designated students to rate his performance in every class based on a questionnaire so that he can work on making the learning experience better. This is similar to Lisak *et al.* (2016)' attributing the willingness to take and give feedback as a characteristic of credible leaders.

The influence of Credible Leadership on Leader-follower Relationship

Table 7 How has your credibility affected your relationship with students?

Interviewee	Response
1	Capacity development and strong character formation. I had a student from Cameroun whom I saw potential for greatness in. I counselled with him and began studying with on weekly basis. I show interest in him beyond his academic. By the end of two years, he was seen as the best well behave international student and encouraged for further studies
2	They have more respect for me, some of them come for mentoring
3.	Some of the students come for mentoring

Table 8: How has your credibility affected your relationship with teaching and non-teaching staff?

Interviewee	Response
1	Shared vision and value Source/motivation to put in the best.
2	Teamwork, build team spirit together, there is referral among the staffs
3.	Some of the staffs also come for mentoring

Table 9: What are the possible benefits of Credible Leadership?

Interviewee	Response
1	Satisfaction, sense of fulfilment
2	Fulfilment – it is possible to fruitful without being faithful but it is not possible to be faithful without being fruitful. So, there is this sense of fulfilment. Satisfaction – I feel satisfied seeing people clamping me to succeed. I am blessed – someone bought me a car when the person hears that my car got burnt on motion.
3	Spiritual reward - there is so much joy, there is also blessing – financially, such will be forever remembered, know more people, make new friends, it also calls for more responsibility.

Emergent themes were sharing visions and values, motivation, teamwork, building team spirit together, call for mentoring, meeting new friends, work satisfaction

Shared Visions and Values

Participants reported shared vision and values as an important result of credible leadership in an organisation. Participants believe that their ability to motivate everyone in their organisation has led to the possession of shared vision and values. That is similar to Lisak, *et al's.*, (2016) suggestion that a shared innovation goal amplifies the use of a shared and common language which serves as an important alignment process for different individuals to achieve peak performance in a cohesive environment.

Work Satisfaction

Participants reported that their authenticity has given them and their followers (students and staff) satisfaction with their work thereby corroborating Mrak *et al's* (2021) observation that organisational performance and effectiveness improved significantly as a result of authentic leadership. This also aligns with the position of Lisbona *et al.* (2021) who noted that authentic leadership increased initiative of employees, team culture and reduced burnout of employee.

Call for Mentoring

Two of the participants have mentioned that followers' desire for their mentorship due to their credibility as educational leaders which is evident in their character, performance and relationship with others. Followers calling for the mentorship of their leaders can be explained by Kouzes and Posner's (2011) attraction to the high performance of credible leaders.

Conclusion

This qualitative study examined the role of authentic or credible leadership on the relationship between leaders and followers in the higher educational institution. This was achieved by examining the activities that lead to the development of credibility in leaders, the qualities of credible leadership and the effect of credibility on the leader-follower relationship. Results from analysing emergent themes from the qualitative data collected corroborate findings from extant literature on the qualities and characteristics of credible leadership. The findings also revealed that credible leadership affects the relationship between leaders and followers by improving the leader's conflict resolution ability, followers' development or competence building and open communication predicated on the willingness to receive feedbacks. The study recommends that educational leaders improve their conflict resolution ability, improve competence through self-development and embrace an environment of free and open communication. The study also recommends that future studies should conduct quantitative empirical studies on the effect of credible or authentic leadership on the leader-follower relationship.

References

- Arda, Ö. A., Aslan, T., & Alpan, L. (2016). Review of practical implications in authentic leadership studies. *Procedia, Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 229, 246-252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.07.135>
- Avolio, B. J., & Walumbwa, F. O. (2014). Authentic leadership theory, research and practice: Steps taken and steps that remain. In D. V. Day (Ed.), *The Oxford handbook of leadership and organizations* 331–356. Oxford University Press.
- Baquero, Delgado, Escortell, and Sapena. (2019). Authentic leadership and job satisfaction: A fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA). *Sustainability (Basel, Switzerland)*, 11(8), 2412. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11082412>
- Campos, M. I. d., & Rueda, F. J. M. (2019). Authentic leadership: A theoretical thematic analysis of the contemporary Brazilian Leader's speech. *Paidéia Cadernos De Psicologia e Educação*, 29 <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-4327e2924>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative & mixed methods approaches* (5th, international student ed.). SAGE.

- Fox, J., Gong, T., & Attoh, P. (2015). The impact of principal as authentic leader on teacher trust in the K-12 educational context. *Journal of Leadership Studies (Hoboken, N.J.)*, 8(4), 6-18. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jls.21341>
- Gentry, W. A., Cullen, K. L., Sosik, J. J., Chun, J. U., Leupold, C. R., & Tonidandel, S. (2013). Integrity's place among the character strengths of middle-level managers and top-level executives. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 24(3), 395-404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2012.11.009>
- Hinojosa, A. S., Davis McCauley, K., Randolph-Seng, B., & Gardner, W. L. (2014). Leader and follower attachment styles: Implications for authentic leader-follower relationships. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 25(3), 595-610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2013.12.002>
- Iszatt-White, M., Carroll, B., Gardiner, R. A., & Kempster, S. (2021). Leadership Special Issue: Do we need Authentic Leadership? Interrogating authenticity in a new world order. *Leadership*, 17(4), 389-394. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17427150211000153>
- Jamshed, S. (2014). "Qualitative research method-interviewing and observation." *Journal of basic and clinical pharmacy*, 5, 4: 87. doi:10.4103/0976-0105.141942.
- Kouzes, J. M., & Posner, B. Z. (2011). *Credibility: How leaders gain it and lose it, why people demand it* (Kindle Edition). Jossey-Bass.
- Lisak, A., Erez, M., Sui, Y., & Lee, C. (2016). The positive role of global leaders in enhancing multicultural team innovation. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 47(6), 655-673. doi:10.1057/s41267-016-0002-7
- Lisbona, A., Las Hayas, A., Palací, F. J., & Frese, M. (2021). Initiative in work teams: Lever between authentic leadership and results. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(9), 4947. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18094947>
- Mrak, M. K., telan, & Kvasic, S. G. (2021). The mediating role of hotel employees' job satisfaction and performance in the relationship between authentic leadership and organisational performance. *Management (Split, Croatia)*, 26(1), 97-110. <https://doi.org/10.30924/mjcmi.26.1.6>
- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), 533-544. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y>
- Prakash Nair, B., Prasad, T., & Nair, S. K. (2021). Self-awareness trigger leading to authentic leadership: Conceptualization and development of reliable and valid self-awareness trigger scale. *Dynamic Relationships Management Journal*, 10(1) <https://doi.org/10.17708/DRMJ.2021.v10n01a02>
- Sarkar, A. (2019). Authentic leadership: The influence of work and non-work domain contextual factors. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 40(4), 520-531 <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-06-2018-0224>
- Stahl, G. K., Maznevski, M. L., Voigt, A., & Jonsen, K. (2010). Unraveling the effects of cultural diversity in teams: A meta-analysis of research on multicultural work groups. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 41(4), 690-709. doi:10.1057/jibs.2009.85
- Steffens, N. K., Wolyniec, N., Okimoto, T. G., Mols, F., Haslam, S. A., & Kay, A. A. (2021). Knowing me, knowing us: Personal and collective self-awareness enhances authentic leadership and leader endorsement. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 101498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2021.101498>
- Williams, E. N., Grande, S., Nakamura, Y. T., Pyle, L., & Shaw, G. (2021). The development and practice of authentic leadership: A cultural lens. *European Journal of Training and Development, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print)*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJTD-03-2021-0039>
- Wirawan, H., Jufri, M., & Saman, A. (2020). The effect of authentic leadership and psychological capital on work engagement: The mediating role of job satisfaction. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 41(8), 1139-1154. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-10-2019-0433>